

The number of data to construct n-gons with exercises and solutions

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If we view at an arbitrary triangle, we need 3 data to construct the triangle. These can be sides or angles.

Now we look at a quadrangle. If we construct 3 sides, the fourth side is determined, too. Then the quadrangle is constructed. To construct these 3 sides, we need 2 angles. With that we need 5 data to construct a general quadrangle, see figure.

We can do the same with the n-gon. If we construct $n - 1$ sides, the n . side is determined. But to construct $n - 1$ sides we need $n - 2$ angles as we can see in the figure.

With that the number of data is:

$$z_k = n - 1 + n - 2 = 2n - 3$$

This formula is valid for $n \geq 3$.

1 The construction formula at n-gon circumscribing and inscribed n-gon:

If we construct a n-gon circumscribing we must know the incircle radius and one angle. The other data can be sides or angles. On this way we need the incircle radius and an angle and $n - 2$ other data. These $n - 2$ data can be sides or angles. With that a n-gon circumscribing needs n data to be constructed.

At an inscribed n-gon we require the exterior circle radius and $n - 1$ other data (sides or angles). With that we need n data to construct a inscribed n-gon, too.

Conclusions: The general n -gon requires $2n - 3$ data to be constructed, but the n -gon circumscribing and the n -gon inscribed need only n data. With that the n -gon circumscribing and the n -gon inscribed have got $2n - 3 - n = n - 3$ other conditions.

Some examples:

A triangle needs no other conditions. Every triangle has got an exterior circle and an incircle. At quadrangle circumscribing and quadrangle inscribed there is one condition.

Quadrangle circumscribing:

The sum of the opposite sides must be equal.

Quadrangle inscribed:

The sum of the opposite angles is 180° .

Exercises:

1. How many data is needed to construct a 123-gon respectively a 500-gon?
2. Which n -gon needs 1575 (909) data for construction?

3. We view a 64-gon circumscribing and an inscribed 204-gon. How many data is needed to construct these polygons? How many additional conditions exist?
4. Which n -gon circumscribing needs 689 additional conditions? Which inscribed n -gon needs 1999 additional conditions?

Solutions to the exercises:

To exercise 1:

The formula for the quantity of construction data is $2n - 3$. At 123-gon is the quantity $2 \cdot 123 - 3 = 243$. At 500-gon we obtain $2 \cdot 500 - 3 = 997$.

To exercise 2:

The formula for the quantity of construction data is $2n - 3$. We must solve to n . We find:

$$2n - 3 = 1575 \qquad 2n - 3 = 909$$

It follows:

$$n = \frac{1575 + 3}{2} = 789 \qquad n = \frac{909 + 3}{2} = 456$$

It is a 789-gon and a 456-gon.

To exercise 3:

At n -gon circumscribing and inscribed n -gon n data for construction are necessary. With that the quantity of data is 64 respectively 204.

The quantity of additional conditions at n -gon circumscribing and at inscribed n -gon is $n - 3$. With that we have 61 respectively 201 additional data.

To exercise 4:

The formula for the quantity of additional conditions at n -gon circumscribing and inscribed n -gon is $n - 3$. We must solve to n . We must add only 3. With that we have a 692-gon circumscribing and an inscribed 2002-gon.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "The n -gon with exercises and solutions" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002